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Strategic Exploitation Plan

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Partners short names

ENVI	Environment Park Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Hidrogeno
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodородen Klaster

Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
BG	Background data
FG	Foreground data
R	Results
KER	Key Exploitable Results
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
CC L	Creative Commons License

Executive Summary

Sound Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is essential to enable the successful exploitation of HYPOP's Results. Therefore, the consortium of HYPOP has great interest in managing innovation and IPR in the framework of the project, with a view to effectively paving the way for the exploitation and sustainability of its results following its completion.

The current report presents the **first version** of the HYPOP's **Strategic Exploitation Plan**, encompassing the project's Innovation and IPR Management Strategy. This document sheds light on the key terms and procedures pertaining to the management and protection of intellectual property, lays down the main components of the relevant methodology which will be adopted throughout the project (IPR Matrix methodology) and describes the initial results of its implementation, in terms of **Background IP** and **Key Exploitable Results (KER)**.

Along these lines, an overview of HYPOP's Key Exploitable Results as envisioned at this stage of the project is presented, along with the partners' initial plans for their post-project exploitation.

The report will be elaborated and updated at the end of the project, when all the services of the project have been developed and validated. With that in mind, the final version of the Strategic Exploitation Plan will be developed on M24. This final version will specifically describe the project's KERs and their main exploitation routes, the target groups per project KER, the general terms of use of each KER and the relevant IPR provisions, the joint exploitation plans for the consortium as well as per individual project partner (or groups of partners), the means and procedures for the exploitation of the KERs and a roadmap to this end.

However, considering the overall project's objective to raise awareness and trust on the hydrogen technologies, the HYPOP exploitation strategy is based on the exploitation maximization of project's results sharing in open or copyrights protection formats to reach the specific stakeholders in wider way, then accelerating the development of the European hydrogen economy.

1 Introduction

The HYPOP partners are committed to producing results that will be sustainable after the project's completion, all while ensuring that innovative ideas emerging from the project are fully investigated in terms of exploitation potential. To this end, HYPOP places great emphasis not only on managing the **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** of the partners' ideas and project results, but also on mapping out the expected uses and benefits of each HYPOP Key Exploitable Result (KER), with a view to effectively paving the way for smooth exploitation and sustainability of its results, following the completion of the project.

With that in mind, the current document represents the **first version** of the HYPOP **Strategic Exploitation Plan** which will serve as the basis for the activities to be carried out in the framework of WP5 towards sound innovation management as well as towards exploitation and sustainability of the project's results after the end of the project. The document is correlated to other deliverables of the project, that might influence the overall exploitation plan along the project and here reported:

- D5.1 First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
- D5.4 Networking with other projects and initiatives Report
- Final Progress Report

This initial version of HYPOP Strategic Exploitation Plan comprises 8 chapters, as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the context in which this report has been elaborated, its relation to other project activities, as well as to its structure.
- **Chapter 2** clarifies key terms pertaining to IPR management, defines the underlying objectives in the framework of the project and offers an overview of intellectual property protection instruments that could be employed.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the Innovation and IPR management strategy and its underlying stages in the context of HYPOP and describes the methodology to be adopted in this respect.
- **Chapter 4** introduces the IPR Matrix and explains the procedures followed to identify the HYPOP background IP and Results as well as the project's key exploitable results, as perceived at this stage of the project.
- **Chapter 5** offers a preliminary overview of the background IP and Results of project partners and the project's key exploitable results, as identified at this stage of the project.
- **Chapter 6** describes the exploitation plans per each Partner
- **Chapter 7** Conclusion and next steps.

The HYPOP Strategic Exploitation Plan – Strategy will be updated and further elaborated, according to the project's progress. More specific, its updated and **final version** is expected at the end of the project (**M24**) and will include the final description and owners of the project's Key Exploitable Results as well as their plans regarding IP protection and valorization, which are expected to facilitate exploitation after the end of the project.

2 IPR Management overview

The following subsections aim to set the objectives of the IPR management strategy as well as to clarify the main terms concerning the key elements of IPR management, which represent the principal aspects of the IPR management procedures of the project.

2.1 Objectives

HYPOP's IPR management objectives embrace the need to protect project's KERs in order to handle and manage efficiently all the outcomes that will stem during the project's life span with a view to ensuring the exploitation and dissemination of HYPOP's Key Exploitable Results.

To this end, the main objectives of the HYPOP's Innovation and IPR Management Strategy are the following:

- Define and describe the IPR management methodology to be followed within the context of HYPOP during the project;
- Identify the Results that will emerge from the activities foreseen within the lifecycle of the project thus determining a Results' portfolio from the initial stages of the project;
- Develop a collective understanding among HYPOP's partners, concerning key terms and issues revolving around the background IP and Results and respective access rights;
- Assess and conceptualize a preliminary framework of the IP protection that will be employed for each identified key exploitable result of HYPOP;
- Monitor, identify and eventually resolve any conflicts that may arise in terms of IP within the consortium and beyond if applicable;
- Establish common guiding routes and actions within the consortium to safeguard the smooth operation of the IPR strategies to be implemented.
- In general, the key concepts to consider for designing the Innovation and IPR management strategy of Horizon Europe projects are the following¹:
 - Background
 - Results
 - Key Exploitable Results
 - Dissemination
 - Access rights

Therefore, the following subsections aim to clarify the main terms concerning the key elements of IPR management, which represent key aspects of the IPR management procedures of the project.

¹ European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, [Your guide to Intellectual Property Management in Horizon Europe](#), Publications Office, 2022

2.2 Background

Background IP means any **data expertise or information** – whatever is form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that is:

- Held by the partners before they acceded to the Agreement and
- Needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Agreement².

2.3 Results or Foreground (FG)

By the term Results or Foreground (FG), any tangible or intangible output of the project is meant, such as data, knowledge, or information, which is generated in the project, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights³. In this respect, project Results can arise and be obtained from project partners to protect and exploit the underlying Key Exploitable Results of the project which include intellectual property rights (e.g., copyrights, industrial designs, patents). It should be noted that results generated outside the project activities cannot be defined as project results.

As indicated in table 5, a specific foreground is defined for each WP and each related developed activity

2.4 Key Exploitable Results (KER)

Exploitation of project's results means the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities⁴.

Under this scheme, a Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result (either the whole result or a part of it) or a combination of results, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits – downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or

² See Article 16.1 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

³ See Article 16.2 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

⁴ See Annex 5 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

education⁵. To this end, not all project results may meet the above conditions and be identified as Key Exploitable Results.

2.5 Access Rights

Access rights refer to user rights for requesting access to a project partner’s background and results in order to implement its activities under the project or to use its own results. In addition, access rights can be utilized as long as they are needed for exploiting the project’s results. The granting of access rights within a collaborative Horizon Europe project follows specific rules pre-defined in the Grant Agreement⁶ and the Consortium Agreement⁷. Depending on their purpose of use, access rights within HYPOP are depicted in the following table.

Purpose for Access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Project implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royalty-free Unless otherwise agreed in Attachment 1 of Consortium Agreement 	Royalty-free
Exploitation of Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access rights to results for internal research and for teaching activities on a royalty free basis. Fair and reasonable conditions A request for Access Rights may be made up to six months after the end of the Project or after the termination of the requesting Party’s participation in the Project. 	

Table 1 - Access Rights

2.6 Protection of Results

Protection of Results constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale, or commercialization of IP in the form of products and services. Moreover, its utilization is vital for prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it can contribute to support the branding of products and services both to customers and investors.

When considering IP protection, it must be noted that IP results can be protected by several types of IPR, and consequently, the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The selection of the most suitable form of IP protection depends on the nature and specific characteristics of the results under consideration and the objectives of the IP owner.

There are various types of instruments that may be considered for protecting IP:

⁵ HEU Results Platform, [Introducing the Horizon Results Platform and Horizon Results Platform TV](#)

⁶ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

⁷ See Section 9 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement

- Trademarks
- Patents
- Utility Models
- Copyrights
- Trade secrets
- Confidentiality Agreements

Under the frame of HYPOP, meaningful IP protection instruments that can be used are the following:

- Copyrights and Creative Common License (CC)
- Confidentiality agreements.

Further details with respect to each of the above-mentioned protection instruments are provided in the subsections below, even if not all directly applicable in HYPOP Project.

2.6.1 Trademarks and Service Marks

Trademarks

A trademark constitutes an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered⁸. Trademarks consist of signs capable of distinguishing the products (either goods or services) of a trader from those of others. The main function of a trademark is to identify the commercial origin of a product. This does not mean that it must inform the consumer of the actual person who has manufactured the product or even the one who is trading in it. It is sufficient that the consumer can trust in each enterprise, not necessarily known to him, being responsible for the product sold under the trademark.

Service Marks

In modern trade, consumers are offered not only a vast choice of goods of all kinds but also with an increasing variety of services which tend increasingly to be offered on a national and even international scale. There is therefore also a need for signs that enable the consumers to distinguish between the different services such as insurance companies, car rental firms, airlines, etc.

These signs are called service marks and fulfil the same origin-indicating and distinguishing function for services as trademarks do for goods. Since service marks are signs that are similar in nature to trademarks, the same criteria can be applied. Thus, service mark protection has sometimes been

⁸ European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, [Your guide to IP in Europe, Publication Office](#), 2019, p.5

introduced by a short amendment to the existing trademark law, simply providing for the application to service marks of the provisions on the protection of trademarks⁹.

2.6.2 Patents

A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) offering a new technical solution or facilitating a new way of doing something. The patent holder enjoys the exclusive right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting their invention for a limited period. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application¹⁰.

A patent does not give its owner the positive right to use the patented invention. Third party rights may have to be requested. Still, a patent owner has the right to decide who may or may not use the patented invention throughout the period during which the invention is protected. Moreover, the patent owner may give permission to other parties, or license them, to use the invention on mutually agreed terms. The owner may also sell the right to the invention to someone, who then becomes the new owner of the patent. Finally, patents are granted only country by country, some regionally, and may also be used in non-patented territories.

Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and the invention becomes part of the public domain, in the sense that the owner no longer holds exclusive rights in it, and it becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others¹¹.

2.6.3 Utility Models

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorization, for a limited period¹². The inclusion of utility models into the intellectual property system in some countries has the primary objective of nurturing the rapid evolution of indigenous innovativeness, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises and among individuals¹³.

⁹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 68

¹⁰ See [Your Guide to IP in Europe](#) for the definition of patents in the European context

¹¹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 17

¹² Definition of utility models in the European context retrieved from [Your Guide to IP in Europe](#)

¹³ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40

2.6.4 Copyrights and Creative Commons License

Copyright (or author's right) is the term used to describe the rights that creators have over their literary, scientific, and artistic works. There is not an exhaustive list containing the works that can be protected by copyright. However, several pieces of work are usually covered by copyright at international level¹⁴:

- Literary works such as novels, poems, plays, newspaper
- Articles
- Computer programs, databases
- Films, musical compositions, and choreographies
- Artistic works such as paintings, drawings, photographs
- Sculptures
- Architecture, and advertisements, maps, and technical drawings

Copyright protection also includes moral rights, including the right to claim authorship of a work, and the right to oppose changes to it that could harm the creator's reputation. The creator - or the owner of the copyright in a work - can enforce rights administratively and in the courts, by inspection of premises for evidence of production or possession of illegally made "pirated" goods related to protecting works. The owner may obtain court orders to stop such activities, as well as seek damages for loss of financial rewards and recognition. Finally, it is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original¹⁵.

A very common and useful copyright tool that is applied is the **Creative Commons License (CC)**, which forge a balance inside the traditional "all rights reserved" setting that copyright law creates. These copyright licenses and tools give everyone from individual creators to large companies and institutions a simple, standardized way to grant copyright permissions to their creative work. There are several Creative Commons Licenses and each one helps the creators retain copyright while allowing others to copy, distribute, and make some uses of their work, at least non-commercially. Furthermore, every Creative Commons license ensures creators get the credit for their work they deserve, and also works around the world and lasts as long as applicable copyright lasts (because they are built on copyright). The set of Creative Commons licenses is composed of the following licenses¹⁶:

¹⁴ European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, [Your guide to IP in Europe](#), Publications Office, 2019, p.33

¹⁵ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40

¹⁶ For more information about Creative Commons licenses visit: [CreativeCommons.org](https://creativecommons.org)

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

2.6.5 Trade Secrets

Any confidential business information providing a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. The type of information that can be protected as a trade secret is therefore highly diverse. It can include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes or manufacturing processes¹⁷.

2.6.6 Confidentiality Agreements

Confidentiality is an extremely critical issue for participants in innovation projects, from the setting-up to the implementation and exploitation phases. Exchanging valuable information with other partners is a necessity that regularly occurs in collaborative initiatives or undertakings. Accordingly, confidentiality issues and measures should be taken into consideration to safely exchange information, facilitating the project development, and ensuring the non-disclosure of sensitive technology, business or commercially confidential information. Confidentiality agreements provide protection and more security to an organisation that is about to share or make available information to another organisation by ensuring that confidential information will be used only for the permitted purposes agreed between the signatories of the agreement and will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent. Therefore, the signature of a confidentiality agreement can be seen as a very important step to keep confidential information secret in order to maintain a competitive edge¹⁸.

¹⁷ European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, [Your guide to IP in Europe](#), Publications Office, 2019, p.29

¹⁸ See Non-Disclosure Agreement of European IPR Helpdesk: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/One-Way-Non-Disclosure-Agreement-EN-1_2021.pdf

3 IPR management strategy

Under the frame of HYPOP, key IP and innovation management will be employed, with a view to setting a common understanding concerning the background, results, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, dissemination and exploitation during and after the project development. In this respect, the HYPOP IPR management strategy applies a comprehensive framework which separates the IP management processes of the project in the following stages:

- Start of the Project
- During Project Implementation
- After Project End

In this respect, the following figure illustrates the IPR management stages, as considered within HYPOP. More details about these stages are shown below.

Figure 1 - HYPOP IPR Management Stages

3.1 Start of the Project

Both the **Grant Agreement** and the **Consortium Agreement** constitute documents which include a description of several issues related to IPR. Their unique provisions represent a reference point for

IPR issues within the project partners. In this respect, any further advancements regarding IPR actions to be put in place by project partners will be facilitated under the underlying provisions.

3.1.1 Grant Agreement (GA)

The Grant Agreement constitutes a contract which sets out the key rules and conditions of the project and is conducted between the EC and the HYPOP partners. It represents the main contractual basis for HYPOP while its main points and sections referring to IPR are included in **Section 2 “Specific Rules for carrying out the Action”¹⁹**. Under this scheme, the management of the HYPOP IP is regulated, whereas access rights and obligations related to the background are set. In addition, the GA defines issues concerning the ownership and protection of the project’s generated results, as well as their exploitation and dissemination. Finally, transferability and access rights to results are also defined in the HYPOP GA.

3.1.2 Consortium Agreement (CA)

The Consortium Agreement constitutes a contract among the partners of HYPOP consortium which aims to define rights and obligations within the partnership for the purposes of conducting the project’s foreseen actions and activities²⁰. The CA minimizes the probability of later disputes as it provides rules and responsibilities during the project as well as defines the access rights to be granted to the partners concerning the project. In addition, rights and responsibilities are outlined among the consortium members concerning issues of the IP.

The HYPOP Consortium Agreement main points and sections referring to IPR are contained in:

- **Section 8 “Results”**, that sets out provisions on ownership and joint ownership of results, as well as on their transfer and dissemination
- **Section 9 “Access Rights”**, which clarifies the access rights governing principles along with the access rights for the exploitation and dissemination purposes. It also states specific provisions for access rights to the software
- **Attachment 1 “Background included”** that presents the initial list of usable background IP.

¹⁹ See Article 18 and Annex 5 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

²⁰ See Section 2 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement

3.1.3 Definition of Background

At the start of the project, all project partners must identify the background that is pertinent for the project actions and grant access rights to this IP, in principle²¹. The background of a project can be identified and agreed within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, considering two main aspects:

- **Identification of background:** Naming of the background IP that each project partner provides to the consortium, and which are imperative for successful implementation and exploitation of the project actions
- **Definition of Access Rights:** Clarification of the rights to use knowledge under the terms and conditions agreed within the consortium and in align with the underlying background rules and obligations set by the EC in order to ensure the smooth implementation of the project.

3.2 During Project Implementation

During the implementation stage of the project, IP handling procedures are foreseen to be applied among the HYPOP partners to properly organize results management of the project. In this respect, as the project evolves, the focus will be on project results identification, ownership, access rights, and protection of results, as well as exploitation. HYPOP IPR management emphasizes the establishment of robust handling procedures of IPR issues that are of strategic importance to the project to facilitate exploitation of its results.

Therefore, partners should focus on two different points:

- **Providing access rights to their knowledge** for other partners to carry out their work on the project
- **Establishing early result identification procedures** with a view to protecting, disseminating, and exploiting the project's key exploitable results, all while fostering long-term cooperation among partners and efficient project management.

In this respect, key IP related issues in the HYPOP implementation phase include:

²¹ See Attachment 1 in the Consortium Agreement for a detailed description of the HYPOP background and the access rights granted in principle for the consortium.

3.2.1 Background identification

During the project implementation stage, it is imperative to identify the relevant Background items, if any, complementary to those outlined in the Consortium Agreement. To this end, any partner may add additional Background to Attachment 1 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement during the project, provided they give written notice to other partners. However, in case that a partner wishes to modify or withdraw its Background in Attachment 1, approval of the General Assembly will be needed according to the Consortium Agreement provisions²².

3.2.2 Results identification

A core process of the HYPOP IP management is the project results' identification with a view to creating a concrete mapping of the project's results and enhancing the HYPOP IP portfolio. Therefore, all valuable IP within the project must be identified, listed, named, described and analyzed in a systematic way.

3.2.3 Ownership of Results

The Grant Agreement of HYPOP establishes that the results of the project are owned by the partner(s) that generates them. Given the collaborative nature of the project, an individual result can be jointly developed by two or more partners and its joint ownership is subject to the agreement on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership²³. Although regulations concerning the frame of joint ownership are embedded in the HYPOP Consortium Agreement²⁴, partners may establish during the project implementation a separate joint ownership agreement in order to define the allocation and terms of exercising their ownership.

Moreover, according to the [Europe Horizon reporting template](#), HYPOP partners are requested to prepare a **Results Ownership List** to clarify ownership of project results and to facilitate the process for exploitation of these by project partners and, where relevant, third parties. As a minimum, the list should include details of whether the result has single or joint ownership, the name of the owner(s), the country of establishment of the owner(s) and whether the results will be exploited by the owner(s). The Results Ownership List will be prepared and included in the final version of Exploitation Plan as well as in the **Final Periodic Report**, where the ownership of projects results will be fully defined amongst HYPOP partners.

²² See Section 9 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement

²³ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

²⁴ See Paragraph 8.2 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement

3.2.4 Protection of Results

Effective exploitation of the innovative concepts and KERs developed under the frame of HYPOP depends on the protection of the project’s results. Consortium partners are bound by the terms of their grants and must adequately protect their results, for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage, if²⁵:

- The project’s results can be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited and,
- Protecting them is possible and justified (given the circumstances)

In this respect, when considering IP protection HYPOP partners must consider their own legitimate interests, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, along with the legitimate interests of the whole consortium and any other legitimate interests. The table that follows illustrates the different protection instruments that can be applied to a variety of subjects.

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility Model	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Invention	X	X			X
Software	X*	X	X		X
Scientific Article			X		
Technology Design			X	X	
Name of Technology				X	
Know How	X	X			X
Website			X	X	X

*Software patentability is still a debated issue given its exclusion as subject matter as by Article 52(2)(c) and (3) of the European Patent Convention (EPC). Source: IPR Helpdesk.

Table 2 - Protection Instruments of Results

3.2.5 Exploitation of Results

The identified Key Exploitable Results of HYPOP will be exploited as foreseen within the HYPOP Grant Agreement²⁶. Particularly, consortium partners should be fully aware that they must, up to four years after project completion, use their best efforts to ensure exploitation of their results, either directly or indirectly by another entity, through transfer or licensing.

If, despite the best effort for exploitation, no uptake happens within the following year after the end of the project, the partners must use the [Horizon Results Platform](#) to make exploitable results visible to

²⁵ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

²⁶ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

potential interested entities, unless obligation is waived, which is free and part of the [Funding & Tenders Portal](#).

To this end, the HYPOP consortium will seek exploitation opportunities of the project's results in (i) further research activities (outside the action), (ii) developing, creating or marketing a product or process, (iii) creating and providing a service, (iv) using them in standardization activities or other use scenarios such as to inform policy or for educational purposes. Hence, exploitation is by no means limited to commercial exploitation²⁷.

In parallel to the successive phases of IP identification, determination of claims for ownership and exploitation as well as the definition of IP protection measures, further actions will run, including:

- Outlining of potential exploitation routes anticipated for each of HYPOP's KERs beyond the end of the project
- Elaboration of the HYPOP Exploitation Plan to serve as the road map for the roll-out of the exploitable results of the project after the end of the Grant.

3.2.6 Dissemination of Results

HYPOP partners are set to select the appropriate means for dissemination of project results (e.g., scientific publications, publication on web sites, conferences, etc.), according to the conditions set forth in the CA and in other specific confidentiality agreements that might arise in order to maintain confidentiality during and after the end of the project²⁸. Additionally, partners must disseminate their results as soon as they are feasible by using publicly available formats in accordance with any restrictions due to IP protection, security rules or legitimate interests and the provisions of GA²⁹.

Along with that, the Open Science approach will be followed by partners, which focuses on spreading knowledge as soon as it is available using digital and collaborative technology. Considering that, HYPOP partners have been invited to make their scientific publications available as Open Access publications, and grant access as open as possible and as closed as necessary³⁰.

It must be noted that all partners should be aware that they first ensure the protection of a project's exploitable result and then proceed to dissemination actions of this or any other underlying result.

²⁷ European Commission, [Your guide to IP management in Horizon Europe](#), p.20

²⁸ See Paragraph 8.4 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement

²⁹ See Article 17 and Annex 5 of the HYPOP Grant Agreement

³⁰ European Commission, [Your guide to IP management in Horizon Europe](#), p.19

3.3 Post Project Stage

At the project's conclusion, the final version of the Strategic Exploitation Plan will be submitted, outlining the use that HYPOP consortium intends to make of its Key Exploitable Results and the related plans and time frame for their exploitation. The plan will describe the further activities that need to be implemented to ensure the use and long-term sustainability of HYPOP Key Exploitable Results. In addition, it will include the final findings concerning IP issues, as well as the final update of the IPR Matrix (See Section 4), detailing the intellectual property rights applied and registered. This deliverable, therefore, will envisage the final strategy of the consortium as shaped at the end of the project for exploitation, management of intellectual property rights and sustainability, including also any selected commercialization pathways if applicable.

At this final stage of the project, consortium partners will employ some basic actions, aiming to ensure the sound post-project management of the innovation and exploitation processes. Typically, they will:

- Explore exploitation strategies and pathways, either joint or not, and agree on the most suitable ones
- Look at IP ownership arrangements and related responsibilities, including the definition of relative contributions of joint-owners, and
- Weigh potential (licensing) agreement and remuneration options linked to the use of IP resulting from the project and options for remuneration.

On the other hand, there will be follow-up by the EC on partners' progress, needs and obstacles on their path towards exploitation two years after the end of the project. Under this frame, HYPOP partners will be called to complete a structured Questionnaire to report on their exploitation state.

3.4 Role of the Exploitation Manager

The Exploitation Manager (EM) is responsible for defining the project's Innovation and IPR Management Strategy, preparing the respective reports and ensuring that innovative ideas which arise during the project will be thoroughly examined and assessed for potential exploitation, while at the same time all background intellectual property and results of the project is managed. To this end, the EM will be in close communication with the Project Coordinator and the General Assembly to ensure continuous feedback from escalating project activities from the start until the project completion.

The Exploitation Manager (EM) will be identified from the HYPOP Partners with a dedicated survey by the end of the first year of project (M12).

The Exploitation Manager will be responsible for the organization and management issues of the HYPOP IPR strategy implementation. It is considered good practice for a partner to inform and consult the EM accordingly before deciding whether to protect the results stemming from its underlying activities or not – particularly if the partner is considering a potential joint IP scheme.

Finally, the EM also assumes a mediation role in case of IP conflicts (see Section 3.6), monitors project activities and feeds the development of the subsequent versions of this report.

3.5 Knowledge Management of the Project

The management of the IP constitutes an integral part of the overall HYPOP project management structure and thus it is important to establish a permanent IP monitoring scheme during the project. In this respect, an efficient IPR management methodology should define, from the early stages of the project, the procedures under which newly generated/ identified results will be handled within the lifespan of HYPOP.

Efficient management of IP in HYPOP will be achieved through adopting a process able to identify IP results as well as to determine their adequate handling and protection. In this respect, it is essential to establish mechanisms that will guarantee that IP information is dependable and timely captured. Should WP Leaders identify a new result that will be generated under their respective WP activities, the Exploitation Manager must be informed accordingly.

The HYPOP EM constitutes the party that will organize the screening and the management of any newly identified results and their corresponding IP issues that arise during the project's lifespan. The EM will direct the consortium partners to establish the most adequate and efficient IPR strategy based on the nature of the newly identified result and the purposes of the HYPOP consortium concerning the exploitation of this result. To facilitate this process, the HYPOP IPR management strategy foresees creating and updating a living IPR Matrix (See section 4) to be revised and extended with new pieces of project results as the project's implementation advances.

3.6 IP Conflicts

To proactively avoid IP conflicts, project partners will be well-informed about IP rules and guided through the exploitation process with the help of the EM and the IPR Matrix. In this respect, partners will identify their IPR results, formulate their ownership and exploitation claims and if deemed necessary, transfer any relevant results to HYPOP's key exploitable results according to the principal rights and obligations defined in the Consortium Agreement of HYPOP (Section 8 of HYPOP CA). The Exploitation Manager will provide assistance for the following indicative (and not exclusive) issues:

- Is there a possible misunderstanding about the definition of the exploitable result and therefore of the object of claims?
- Are there exploitation claims that should be further specified so that the partners can check the compatibility of their claims?
- Are the foreseen exploitation claims compatible with the ownership claims of the partners (related issue of access rights)?
- Are there any confidentiality issues e.g., new knowledge of strategic importance for a partner and consequently the need for a confidential agreement?

Are there any possible IP conflicts between the partners, both related to ownership and the related need for access rights and to exploitation claims?

In terms of IP conflict, the Exploitation Manager will encourage conflicting parties to get in contact and proactively find solutions, making written agreements whenever necessary. In case no agreement is achieved, the internal mediation process will be kicked off following the provisions of section 11.8 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement. In case the IP issues remain unresolved after this first mediation procedure, further mediation processes will be applied according to the HYPOP CA provisions (See Section 11.8 of the HYPOP Consortium Agreement).

4 IPR MATRIX Methodology

The HYPOP IPR management approach foresees the utilization of an IPR Matrix to define the main IPR issues concerning the HYPOP Innovation and IPR Management Strategy. This approach will support all partners in identifying and managing the background knowledge, the results and key exploitable results of the project in order to have a full overview about IP protection and necessary agreements to enable successful exploitation.

The IPR Matrix methodology is comprised of 4 distinct but interconnected steps, as follows:

- **Step 1:** Addition of new Background and definition of access rights among partners within the project according to the CA processes³¹, complementary to the identified BG³² in the HYPOP CA at the start of the project
- **Step 2:** Identification of the planned results under the HYPOP activities
- **Step 3:** Identification of the project’s key exploitable results (as defined at this early stage of the project) and the **partners contributing** to each one along with their corresponding interest for their exploitation
- **Step 4:** Definition of a preliminary framework of IPR protection for the defined HYPOP results, which will enhance their further exploitation.

At this early stage of the project, the objective of the Strategic Exploitation Plan of HYPOP is to define the Key Exploitable Results on the one hand and identify, to the extent possible, the BG and results of the project along with their corresponding access rights on the other hand. During the later stages of the project’s implementation, the Strategic Exploitation Plan will be updated accordingly, in order to capture and integrate the evolvement of the identified results and IPR approach of the project. In particular, the identification of KER would yield the need to establish an ownership regime among project partners for each one of the KER. In addition, rules and conditions to get access to KER need also to be considered. Finally, the selection of the IPR to be employed in each case will follow.

Under this framework, the structure of the IPR Matrix that will be used throughout the duration of the project is summarized below.

Background (BG)	Results (R)	Key Exploitable Results (KER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BG# • Partner’s Background • Short description of BG • Type of protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R# • Project Result • Related WP • Contributing partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KER# • Key Exploitable Result • Main partner

³¹ See Paragraph 9.1.2 of HYPOP Consortium Agreement.

³² See Attachment 1 of HYPOP Consortium Agreement.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conditions to use within HYPOP • Conditions to use outside HYPOP • Interest in further exploitation through HYPOP results • Remarks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short description of R • Related BG# • Type of protection • Conditions to use within HYPOP • Interest in further exploitation of Project Results • Conditions to use after the end of the Project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further contributing partner(s) • Related R# • Related BG# • Proposition for the KER-owner • Short description of the KER • Relevance for IP protection • Exploitation pathways
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Table 3 - Structure of IPR Matrix

4.1 Identification of Background

In the first part of the IPR Matrix, the BG that will be used during the project’s implementation shall be identified, as illustrated in the following figure.

#	Relevant Background (name of background)	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of protection (e.g. patent, copyright, TM, Utility model)	Condition of use within HYPOP (free to use, license fee, restrictions, NDA, etc.)	Condition to use outside HYPOP (e.g. is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? It is currently shared with external? If YES on what conditions?)	Interest in further exploitation through HYPOP’s results (YES/NO)	Remarks

Figure 2 - IPR Matrix Background

In the second column of this part of the IPR Matrix, the project’s BG is listed as identified at the time. In the third column, the name of the partner who owns this background is indicated. For each identified background required for the creation of a result, a specific background number per partner shall be assigned. In column 4, the corresponding background number shall be indicated while column 5 should include a short description of the background. In column 6, partners shall indicate relevant IP protection types for the background in terms of patents, copyright, etc. In the seventh column, the conditions to use the background within the project shall be indicated by each partner, whether there are any restrictions to use the background or not (e.g., free to use). In the eighth column, any conditions for using the background outside the framework of HYPOP is indicated, while in the last column partners shall mention if they have any interest in further exploiting the relevant background through the results of the project.

4.2 Identification of project Results

In the second part of the IPR Matrix, the results of the project are identified, as presented in the following figure.

WP	#	Project Results (R) Achievement	Specific Project results	Main Partners (s)	Related BG number	Short description of FG	R number	Type of protection	Condition of use within HYPOP	Interest in further exploitation of Project Results	Condition to use after the end of Project

Figure 3 - IPR Matrix Results

In the first four columns, the HYPOP results along with the relevant WP, are listed. In the fifth column, the main partner responsible for the Results shall be indicated. In the sixth column, the further contributing partners for the Results shall be indicated as well. In the seventh column, the related background number is attached to the underlying R. In the eighth column, a short text describing the identified R shall be included by the responsible partner. In the ninth column, an R number shall be attached to each result per contributing partner. In the tenth column, partners shall indicate relevant IP protection type(s) for the R (e.g., patent, copyright, etc.). In the next column, the conditions to use the R within HYPOP (e.g., free to use or subject to charges) shall be indicated by each partner whether there are any restrictions to use the R or not. In the twelfth column, the project partners shall describe if they have an interest in exploitation of the project result. Finally, in the last column, the conditions (e.g., free to use, license fee, etc.) to use after the project shall be indicated by the partners.

4.3 Identification of Key Exploitable Results

Based on the identified Results the partners will define their key exploitable results along with the underlying IPR provisions, such as protection, definition of access rights and exploitation pathways.

At this step, the third part of the IPR Matrix was elaborated, which defined the Key Exploitable Results (KER), indicating the main contributors for these results, with the aims:

- To **identify IP ownership and exploitation claims**, as well as pro-actively indicate possible conflicts for each exploitable result; and
- To **support decisions on issues pertaining to IP protection**, in order to timely take the needed steps in this regard, including any potential IP agreements (e.g., for joint ownership, providing access rights or even an NDA for confidentiality).

The following figure provides an illustrative overview of this part of the IPR Matrix.

KER #	Key Exploitable Results	Short Description of KER	Main Partners (s)	Contributor Partners (s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner (s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)

Figure 4 - IPR Matrix Key Exploitable Results

In the first two columns, the number and a short name of the identified exploitable results are listed. In the third column, a short text of the identified KER shall be included. In the following column, the main partner(s) responsible for the KER shall be listed. In the fifth column, other relevant contributing partner(s) for the KER shall be indicated as well. In the sixth column, the related R number shall be indicated, whereas in the seventh column the relevant background number shall be stated. In the eighth column, a proposition of the IP ownership of the KER shall be indicated by the main partner contributing to the creation of the KER. In the next column, the responsible partner shall indicate the relevance for possible IP protection. In the next 5 columns, the exploitation routes are divided into five different categories:

- **M:** Making a product and selling it
- **U:** Using the project result internally for further development, for instance:
 - to develop something else for sale; or
 - for R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research projects.
- **L:** Licensing the project result to third parties
- **S:** Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc
- **O:** Others.

The responsible partner for the KER shall choose which exploitation routes are appropriate in consultation with the contributing partners, the Project Coordinator and the Exploitation Manager. Finally, in the last column, the responsible partner shall indicate which exploitation route would be the most promising.

5 HYPOP'S background, results and key exploitable results

5.1 Background

The Background as preliminary identified in the CA preparation and further elaborated according to the HYPOP CA processes is presented in the following table.

#	Relevant Background	Contributing Partner	BG number	Short description of BG	Type of protection
1	Coordination of Social Perception projects as HYCINTH	CNH2	BG 1	<p>Below the principal CNH2 background in Hydrogen technology's Horizon Europe Founded Project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of Social Perception projects (HYCINT - Grant Agreement n° 621228. - https://hyacinthproject.eu/project/) • Analysis the study of current European and regional policies applying in the targeted European countries. • Qualitative interviews oriented to hydrogen sector and to interpret results of the applications-oriented tool box. • Preparation of dissemination activities in the Spanish region. 	No restrictions

Table 4 - Background

5.2 Results

WP	#	Project result (R)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	R number	Type of protection	Conditions to use within HYPOP	Interest in Further Exploitation of Project Results	Conditions to use after the end of project
1	1.1	State-of-the-art of current H2 implementation in EU	Investigate the current state of H2 implementation in different EU countries according to regional strategies, policies and approaches	ENVI	CNH2, TWEED, BH2C, RIGP, APRE	BG 1	R 1.1.1	Open	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
1	1.2	Secondary analysis on hydrogen Public Opinion Survey	Conduct a secondary analysis of the previously conducted Public Opinion Survey to evaluate hydrogen public opinion	IMI			R 1.2.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
1	1.3	Social media analysis on H2 opinion across EU	Conduct an analysis of public engagement with H2 on social media across the EU27 countries, with a specific focus on the EU13 countries	IMI			R 1.3.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
1	1.4	Public Information Strategy	Understanding public opinion determinants on the FCH tech in media channels and develop a specific public information strategy	IMI	All		R 1.4.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions

WP	#	Project result (R)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	R number	Type of protection	Conditions to use within HYPOP	Interest in Further Exploitation of Project Results	Conditions to use after the end of project
2	2.1	Stakeholders' requirements analysis on safety approach	Identify the different safety Countries approaches and the safety barriers, in order to create a map of the main requirements	ENVI	CNH2, TWEED, BH2C, RIGP		R 2.1.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
2	2.2	Stakeholders' requirements analysis on permitting approach	Identify the different permitting Countries approaches and the barriers, in order to create a map of the main requirements	CNH2	ENVI, TWEED, BH2C, RIGP		R 2.2.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
2	2.3	Stakeholders' requirements analysis on certification approach	Identify the different certification approaches and the barriers, to create a map of the main requirements	ENVI	CNH2, TWEED, BH2C, RIGP		R 2.2.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
3	3.1	S-LCA methodology and indicators for citizens engagement and awareness on H2 technologies	S-LCA methodology for engagement of Hydrogen Technologies players (citizens, researches, SME, etc.)	IME			R 3.1.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
3	3.2	Co-creation workshop for citizens engagement	Workshops and WP1 results will allow to develop informative public strategy and guidelines for citizens.	IMI	APRE, CNH2, TWEED, BH2C, RIGP, ENVI		R 3.2.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions

WP	#	Project result (R)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	R number	Type of protection	Conditions to use within HYPOP	Interest in Further Exploitation of Project Results	Conditions to use after the end of project
4	4.1	S-LCA methodology and indicators tailored for decision makers and stakeholders on H2 technologies	Indicators to involve policy and decision makers in the co creation and stakeholders engagements	IME			R 4.1.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
4	4.2	Co-creation workshops for the stakeholders engagement	Co-creation workshops for the stakeholders engagement and transfer of the results from WP2	B2HC	CNH2, ENVI, TWEED, RIGP, APRE		R 4.2.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
4	4.3	Stakeholders's requirements guidelines	Guidelines and good practices for permitting, authorities, first responders and certification bodies with the results coming by the workshops (Task 4.2).	B2HC	CNH2, ENVI, TWEED, RIGP		R 4.3.1				
4	4.4	Final synthesis guide for evidence-based public engagement about hydrogen technologies	A set of concrete recommendations for HYPOP's stakeholders and for citizens at European and local/regional level to boost trust and awareness on hydrogen	ENVI	CNH2, BH2C, TWEED, RIGP, IMI		R 4.4.1	CC License	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

WP	#	Project result (R)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	R number	Type of protection	Conditions to use within HYPOP	Interest in Further Exploitation of Project Results	Conditions to use after the end of project
			technologies and their systemic benefits. Final guidelines toolkit in a user-friendly communication guide.								
5	5.2	HYPOP website	A web multifunctional tool that will provide the stakeholders with tailored information, best practices, guidelines	APRE	All		R 5.2.1	Open	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
5	5.2	Graphic and informative materials: videos, infographics	Informative materials and tools to raise awareness on the benefits of hydrogen, tackle misperception and build social acceptance for Hydrogen technologies.	APRE	All		R 5.2.2	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
5	5.3	Support the project's engagement activities by reaching out target groups and promoting the initiatives	Involves a broad and balanced audience including all possible social categories interested to the Hydrogen Technologies	APRE	All	BG 1	R 5.3.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions

WP	#	Project result (R)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	R number	Type of protection	Conditions to use within HYPOP	Interest in Further Exploitation of Project Results	Conditions to use after the end of project
5	5.4	Stakeholder database	A database with stakeholders/synergic projects at local, national and European level working on hydrogen technologies development and implementation from different point of views (technical, decision making).	ENVI	All		R 5.4.1	CC License	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions

All the activities described in the above table will be performed in full agreement with the GDPR regulation and to the HYPOP Project's Privacy Policy

Table 5 Results

5.3 Key Exploitable Results

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Short description of KER	Main partner (s)	Contributing Partner(s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)
1	Stakeholder database	A database with stakeholders/synergic projects at local, national and European level working on hydrogen technologies development and implementation from different point of views (technical, decision making).	ENVI	All	R 5.4.1			CC License		X				U
2	HYPOP website	A web multifunctional tool that will provide the stakeholders with tailored information, best practices, guidelines	APRE	All	R 5.2.1			Open		X		X		U

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Short description of KER	Main partner (s)	Contributing Partner(s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)
3	Final synthesis guide for evidence-based public engagement about hydrogen technologies	A set of concrete recommendations for HYPOP's stakeholders and for citizens at European and local/regional level to boost trust and awareness on hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits. Final guidelines toolkit in a user-friendly communication guide.	ENVI	CNH2, BH2C, TWEED, RIGP, IMI	R 4.4.1			CC License		X				U

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Short description of KER	Main partner (s)	Contributing Partner(s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)
4	Public Information Strategy	Understanding public opinion determinants on the FCH tech in media channels and develop a specific public information strategy	IMI	All	R 1.4.1			CC License		X				U
5	Graphic and informative materials: videos, infographics	Informative materials and tools to raise awareness on the benefits of hydrogen, tackle misperception and build social acceptance for Hydrogen technologies.	APRE	All	R 5.2.1			CC License		X				U

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Short description of KER	Main partner (s)	Contributing Partner(s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)
6	Stakeholders' requirements guidelines	Guidelines and good practices for permitting, authorities, first responders and certification bodies with the results coming by the workshops (Task 4.2).	B2HC	CNH2, ENVI, TWEED, RIGP	R 4.3.1			CC License		X				U
7	Secondary analysis on hydrogen Public Opinion Survey	Conduct a secondary analysis of the previously conducted Public Opinion Survey to evaluate hydrogen public opinion	IMI		R 1.2.1			CC License		X				U
8	S-LCA methodology and indicators for citizens engagement and awareness on H2 technologies	S-LCA methodology for engagement of Hydrogen Technologies players (citizens,	IME		R 3.1.1			CC License		X				U

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Short description of KER	Main partner (s)	Contributing Partner(s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)
		researches, SME, etc.)												
9	S-LCA methodology and indicators tailored for decision makers and stakeholders on H2 technologies	Indicators to involve policy and decision makers in the co creation and stakeholders engagements	IME		R 4.1.1			CC License		X				U

All the activities described in the above table will be performed in full agreement with the GDPR regulation and to the HYPOP Project's Privacy Policy

Table 6 - Key Exploitable Results

6 Exploitation plan per each HYPOP Partner

In this section, HYPOP partners have been consulted to define a preliminary Individual Exploitation Plan, considering Results and Key Exploitable Results previously identified. Each Individual Exploitation Plan will be further updated by the end of the project, as planned.

Tables below reports the following information per each partner:

- **Expected benefits from KER exploiting**
- **Individual KER's Exploitation Plans**

Partner Name	APRE
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	<p>Create a dedicated high technologies network for potential participation to future HE Calls</p> <p>Create a continuous dialogue between the principal European players in high and innovative technologies. In particular with researcher, policy maker, industries, SME and Universities</p> <p>Increase the Italian's Hydrogen Technologies awareness and knowledge</p> <p>Engagement of Local and European potential stakeholders</p>
Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	<p>Specific activities to reach the above benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of the social media (Website, YouTube, X, Facebook etc.) • Video and infographics dedicated materials • Workshop and International Conference participation • Networking with similar funded and running Hydrogen HE Projects • Define best practices and rules for Hydrogen acceptance and awareness

Partner Name	CNH2
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	<p>Broadening the hydrogen community and enhancing the communication with other partner and stakeholders, creating synergies and preventing previous mistakes or barriers.</p> <p>Helping the development of hydrogen technologies thanks to a wider knowledge of the different barriers and requirements.</p> <p>Facilitating the spread of hydrogen technologies concepts thanks to the availability of updated and attracting contents (videos, infographics, etc) and the knowledge of the public awareness.</p>
Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	<p>Use of the graphic and informative materials in our dissemination activities</p> <p>Consider the barriers exposed by other partners and stakeholders in the projects that we participate in.</p>

Partner Name	IME
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	Science-based support to sound decision-making processes towards social responsibility in hydrogen-related systems, thereby facilitating the engagement of general society, policy-makers, and other stakeholders.
Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	Delivery of the S-LCA material (KER #8) as public HYPOP deliverables, concerning both the methodology (D4.1) and the case studies (D3.1). Expected use of the proposed methodology to support the social assessment of hydrogen-related systems.

Partner Name	IMI
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	By analysing existing survey data, we will gain a baseline understanding of the public opinion regarding H2 implementation in EU countries in terms of technology understanding and acceptance. Secondary data analysis is instrumental in achieving a more robust angle on the original research. This will inform the development of public engagement co-creation workshops planned for WP3.
Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	IMI is particularly interested in the public awareness of hydrogen fuel cell technologies in Europe. By analysing current research and conducting further public engagement activities, we hope to increase the public's level of awareness of these technologies. The evidence-based public engagement events we have planned, could also inform other projects' operations and public engagement methodologies.

Partner Name	RIGP
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	A set of concrete recommendations for HYPOP's stakeholders at European and local/regional level to ensure the valorisation of the activities in Hydrogen Technologies sector. Specific guideline will developed for each target typology (citizen, stakeholders, etc.)
Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	Clear guidance for stakeholders, especially members of the Cluster of Hydrogen Technologies, on safety and certification and support to obtain permits and authorizations for installing hydrogen technologies in support the development and installation of hydrogen technologies

Partner Name	ENVI
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	As Technology Park for environment and cluster manager, ENVI aims to strenght its contacts' network at national/European levels to enhance partnership and innovation transfer in its territory. ENVI also contributes to the Regional Hydrogen Strategy, therefore it aims to improve the dialogue with the public authorities for a responsible hydrogen technologies implementation process and with the citizens as aware final users. Important efforts are also planned in the facilitation and implementation process of permitting, safety and certification procedures in hydrogen prototype/technologies installation phase. Overall, ENVI expects to improve the conditions for an effective hydrogen technologies deployment at territorial level and for the improvement of the hydrogen economy.

Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	Articles, local and European events participation to boost knowledge on the current public opinion within the hydrogen sector and stakeholders; provide guidelines/materials developed by HYPOP to use by the hydrogen actors (e.g. companies, decision makers, communication experts) and adopt a common communication strategy for the awareness and trust improvement on hydrogen technologies with citizens, other than strenght an international stakeholders' community. Other opportunities are consultancy service with companies/public authorities to facilitate the permitting, certification and safety procedures; contribution to the EU research on technical and social activity on hydrogen sector with further projects, collaboration with companies or public entities.
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Partner Name	TWEED
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	Inform and exchange best practices at european level to boost technology developement in Hydroegn value chain and contribute to the implementation of Hydrogen strategies in the different regions. Understand EU maket barriers on regulation, certification or safety to support permits authorization and accelerate H2 pojects dvelopments. Help to sensibilze and engage new stakeholders (end-users, adinistraton,..) in the Hydrogen economy. Know better the hydrogen international community and increase dedicated H2 skills.
Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	TWEED, as a part of Belgian hydrogen Council wich represents the Belgian Hydrogen Industry in Belgium, is seeking to boost cooperation between companies and government by translating European regulations to the various policy levels in Belgium. TWEED will use the dedicated materials to increase awereness in Wallonia/Belgium, use the european best practices learnings to exploit it in our regional/national context, use the specific database to diffuse it to our Belgian's Hydrogen Community, use our network, communciation skills and activities (workshops,...) to spread out the the KER's,...

Partner Name	BH2C
Expected benefits from KER exploiting	<p>Expected results of the conducted surveys related to the project - HYPOP</p> <p>In view of the two types of surveys, namely aimed at experts, representatives of institutional bodies in the Republic of Bulgaria and suppliers and developers of hydrogen technologies again on the territory of the country.</p> <p>Our team expects and predicts that the polls will increase public awareness, reliability and open opportunity to all interested organizations, institutions and companies about the opportunity that is being discovered, in and during the integration of hydrogen technologies in the energy processes of our daily life, industry, productions, innovation and scientific research activities.</p> <p>The spectrum, in relation to the scope of the surveys, their orientation and significance, will help to determine the position of Bulgaria, as a geopolitical, geostrategic and geoeconomics factor, in relation to EU directives, policies and strategies referring to the implementation and production of hydrogen technologies, in particular green hydrogen and the regulatory frameworks that we, as a member state of the European Union, observe, apply and implement.</p>
Individual KER's Exploitation Plans	<p>Using the information received, our team will analyse:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in which projects for hydrogen and hydrogen technologies, the respondents participated, realized or were part of; - who are the main authorities/certifying authorities for safety, security and proper integration of hydrogen solutions; - what legislative acts, regulations, etc. were part of the documentary project part;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - overview of the main obstacles and barriers that should be discussed at the highest level, local authority, executive authority, national assembly, etc.; - sharing of good practices and experience by developers, engineers in the area and individual sector units; - the areas that have the greatest need for the implementation of hydrogen technologies and solutions; - comments, opinions and advice to improve the regulatory framework for the application of hydrogen technologies from laboratory studies to real environments; - comments, opinions and advice for optimizing production and implementation procedures; - optimization of resources in the energy sector, to implement a smooth transition to decarbonization and a green economy.
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The Exploitation Plans per Key Exploitable Result constitute preliminary plans which have been developed according to the current stage of HYPOP project and will be updated in the final version of Strategic Exploitation Plan on M24.

7 Conclusions and next steps

This initial version of the HYPOP Strategic Exploitation Plan describes the strategy and methodology employed in this respect within the framework of HYPOP, while also providing an overview of its Background and project Results as well its Key Exploitable Results. A dedicated tool, namely the IPR Matrix, has been elaborated to facilitate the identification and management of HYPOP's Key Exploitable Results by project partners.

Accordingly, the Strategic Exploitation Plan of HYPOP will be updated to reflect the final project results along with their protection, ownership, access rights with the support of all partners. The final version of the "Strategic Exploitation Plan" will be elaborated on M24 and provide a more accurate outline of the key exploitable results of the project, the main target groups of external stakeholders.

Next steps for the update of the HYPOP Strategic Exploitation Plan can be here summarized:

- Identification of the Exploitation Manager (EM) by the first year of the project (M12) through dedicated survey;
- Update of the IPR Matrix: a further survey among the partners to identify the final project KERs, related responsible partners, IPR protection etc.;
- Update of the Individual Exploitation Plan for each partner;
- Update of the overall HYPOP Strategic Exploitation Plan by M24.

The final Strategic Exploitation Plan will be elaborated also considering other WP5 activities, as the Task5.4. Networking with other EU-funded projects and collaborations with international hydrogen entities, such as the EU Clean Hydrogen Mission or the Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory, are undertaking in order to maximize the project impacts.

Additionally, the final progress report will encompass the measures that have been taken to protect the partnership's IP as well as the respective IPR agreements, fostering the successful post-project exploitation and sustainability of the project's key exploitable results.

To conclude, HYPOP's activities and results have the potential to accelerate the development of the European hydrogen economy. It is therefore important to guarantee that knowledge and tools generated throughout the project are accessible and easy to implement by hydrogen actors, certification bodies, public authorities and by other identified HYPOP stakeholders. The final Strategic Exploitation Plan will guide the actions implemented by partners to ensure a long-term exploitation of HYPOP's outputs and generate a positive impact into our society.

8 References

.General Reference:

- GRANT AGREEMENT - Project: 101111933 – HYPOP – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-2
- CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT - rev. 0, March 2023

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